

TYPES OF TRANSFORMATIONS IN TRANSLATION

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Annotation: This article is devoted to linguistic unit at the level of a word in the source language, for example, in a certain profession, when any relevant name specific to the culture of the source language appears, a double-field adjective; words denoting objects, phenomena, and elements that are inherent in the original or functionally appropriate for the traditional naming of the culture of the culture, but that do not exist in the culture of translation or have a different management and order.

Key words: profession, linguistic unit, sentence, phenomena, elements, language, activity, transferring, definitions, stylistic, source text, level

"In the process of dividing the text and correcting the translation units, the translated text unit is divided into two types: units that are standardly dependent on the context and standard dependencies. The translation of units in standard contrast is based on typologically loaded lexical and grammatical content of two languages. units are easy to implement. These units are the majority in every plain text and correcting the basis of translation. At the same time, this work comes down to your data with a standard interlanguage for yourself.

Units with non-standard dependencies require special software, as the editing and capabilities may differ for use in two different socio-cultural traditions. Special methods of transformation in the making of this unit are material acquisition of requirements, equipping of ling and psychics.

From a linguistic point of view, when translating such non-standard source texts, the translator has at his disposal three main groups of examples: lexical, grammatical and stylistic.

Lexical examples of a non-standard linguistic unit at the level of a word in the source language, for example, in a certain profession, when any relevant name specific to the culture of the source language appears, a double-field adjective; words denoting objects, phenomena, and elements that are inherent in the original or functionally appropriate for the traditional naming of the culture of the culture, but that do not exist in the culture of translation or have a different management and order. Such words are very important in the translation process, because they are relatively independent of the context and give a different direction to the translated text depending on the choice of the translator. Thus, Russian names of Slavic origin, such as Lyudmila and Svetlana,

transliterate in English as Lyudmila or Svetlana, but of course lose their additional associations from the text: in appearance, Lyudmila is dear to people . , Svetlana factors and interpretation, translation of mixed (parallel) translation phrases is not without losses or comments.

In the grammatical form, when the object of translation is one or another grammatical structure of the source text, from a phrase to a superphrase unit. Compared to lexical problems, these problems are not so difficult for the translator, but they require a specific solution and specific methods. For example, absolute participle phrases often used in English require the grammatical structure of the sentence when translated into Russian: The work had been done, everybody feels a great relief. When the deed was done, everyone felt a great sense of relief. Or: having finished the work, everyone felt a great relief.

Transformations can affect any grammatical form, as well as direct use in these other contexts. When translating from English to Russian, there is often no existence between the possibilities of verbs, noun phrases and other grammatical units due to differences in cultural and speech traditions in relation to this context, rather than typological differences. For, in the tradition of English culinary recipes, the imperative is mainly used as a form of expression of the act of cooking, and in Russian as an indefinite form that corresponds to the form of the required verb. person singular + particle -sya: Cook the charred ones until light golden. Buns are baked until golden.

This type of transformation is one of grammar, which consists of gram o' Edit the nature of the grammatical form, if the original form is absent in the studied language or fulfills other problems.

Apart from grammatical substitutions, the most common grammatical changes can be additions, deletions, antonymic translations, etc.

Stylistic translation methods are used when the object of translation is stylistically determined units of the source text. Among the most common stylistic forms there is a metaphor, the translation of which largely depends on how close or distant the cultural and speech traditions of the source and translation languages are to each other. In the English text, metaphor is often playful in nature and contains not only the image itself, but also a more or less clear shade of meaning.

Preservation of the verbal content of the original text leads to a clear conflict with the transfer of stylistic effect, therefore, during translation, this text is changed in order to preserve the whole complex of emotional, evaluative and

semantic associations, and thus contribute to it. to create an absurd-grotesque image of a medical examination. The only sure way to preserve some of these associations that form the basis of the original image is to try to recreate the original combination of stylistic devices, although the words and devices themselves may have changed. As a result, the source text in the Russian translation may look, for example, like this:

In general, the main methods of stylistic transformation include verbal composition, image, replacement of path (or figures of speech), removal of figurative meaning, literal translation (with or without annotations).

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